

Black Mesa Photogrammetry: Apple 3

Processing Report

06 April 2023

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	152	Camera stations:	152
Flying altitude:	1.39 m	Tie points:	21,819
Ground resolution:	0.732 mm/pix	Projections:	81,285
Coverage area:	29.7 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.569 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
2+ (3.7mm)	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for 2+ (3.7mm).

2+ (3.7mm)

152 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	P1	P2
F	2426.73	0.12	1.00	0.02	-0.07	-0.44	0.23	-0.07	0.19	-0.20	0.06	-0.20
Cx	16.8663	0.2		1.00	0.04	0.16	-0.07	0.05	-0.05	0.06	0.91	0.05
Cy	-2.02954	0.2			1.00	-0.18	0.15	-0.06	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.89
B1	-28.2292	0.11				1.00	-0.07	0.04	-0.00	-0.01	0.12	0.08
B2	0.263817	0.087					1.00	0.01	0.01	-0.01	-0.22	0.14
K1	-0.00282777	9.8e-05						1.00	-0.94	0.87	0.04	-0.04
K2	0.00908819	0.00021							1.00	-0.98	-0.04	0.02
K3	-0.012079	0.00014								1.00	0.05	-0.00
P1	0.000602622	2.1e-05									1.00	0.03
P2	0.000896263	1.9e-05										1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
4.87078	2.631	1.98511	5.53594	5.8811

Table 3. Average camera location error.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 2.88 mm/pix
Point density: 12.1 points/cm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	152
Aligned cameras	152
Coordinate system	WGS 84 (EPSG::4326)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	21,819 of 116,419
RMS reprojection error	0.233984 (0.569497 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.645414 (2.83091 pix)
Mean key point size	2.389 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	6.89763

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	High
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	Source
Key point limit	60,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	10 minutes 11 seconds
Matching memory usage	1.67 GB
Alignment time	1 minutes 29 seconds
Alignment memory usage	164.00 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k3, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Optimization time	1 seconds
Date created	2023:03:03 23:07:15
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	13.11 MB

Depth Maps

Count	147
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	23 minutes 47 seconds
Memory usage	2.76 GB
Date created	2023:03:06 14:47:19
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	679.65 MB

Dense Point Cloud

Points	37,655,137
Point colors	3 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
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Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	23 minutes 47 seconds
Memory usage	2.76 GB
Dense cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	49 minutes 45 seconds
Memory usage	6.46 GB
Date created	2023:03:06 15:37:05
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	803.13 MB
Model	
Faces	8,655,166
Vertices	4,330,642
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	23 minutes 47 seconds
Memory usage	2.76 GB
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	21 minutes 58 seconds
Memory usage	6.54 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	5 minutes 37 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	3.29 GB
Blending time	7 minutes 6 seconds
Blending memory usage	2.66 GB
Blending GPU memory usage	1.21 GB
Date created	2023:03:06 16:41:28
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	391.18 MB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.0 build 13794
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	31.85 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-6920HQ CPU @ 2.90GHz
GPU(s)	Quadro M2200